

Speculation of Spin Entropy for an Sz Eigenstate Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 11 2024

In Part I, we noted that a free particle with wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, should have an intrinsic entropy of $\ln(p/\hbar)$. This entropy does not measure the uncertainty of the particle being anywhere in space, but rather the uncertainty within a wavelength gradation which has a uniform probability distribution, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where $1/L = p/\hbar$. In other words, the probability to use follows from $(\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx))/L$ where $1/L = p/\hbar$ and dx is integrated from 0 to L .

This free particle $\exp(ipx)$ entropy differs from a calculation of a bound particle where there is the sense of length in the problem otherwise the particle would not be bound. For example, a crude estimate of this length is that between classical turning points. Thus, x can be integrated between such a length, so to speak and one does not have to adjust the length to a periodic one for $\exp(ipx)$.

We try to apply these ideas to spin entropy.. In (1), an expression for spin entropy is given, but it seems that if one uses an Sz eigenstate, one obtains 0 for the entropy because one knows the state exactly. This is similar to the von Neumann result. We suggest, however, that it seems that one may use the equation of (1) for spin entropy of an eigenstate of Sz measured by someone on the x axis, if one restricts the ϕ angle range to one which makes the interference probability periodic. We consider the example of $s = 3/2$ and $s_z = 3/2$.

Intrinsic Entropy of $\exp(ipx)$

$\exp(ipx)$, a free particle wavefunction, has an intrinsic entropy, we argue. We do not worry about the usual classical entropy linked with the particle being anywhere in space because $L = \infty$ in such a case. We wish to have an intrinsic entropy measure which is linked with the uncertainty of a wavelength and linked to such experiments as 2-slit interference.

We have argued before that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a uniform probability in the length range of \hbar/p . Thus,

$$P(x)dx = dx/L = p/\hbar dx \quad \text{and one integrates from } x=0 \text{ to } x=\hbar/p \quad ((1))$$

This yields an intrinsic free particle entropy of: $\ln(p/\hbar)$. ((2))

The point we wish to make is that when integrating for a free particle, one has to impose a length, \hbar/p , linked to periodicity of the probability $\exp(ipx)$ even though overall $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ represents $P(x)$.

In a bound state problem, one does not have to impose such a length due to periodicity because there is a natural length in the problem, roughly linked to the distance between classical turning points, although one usually integrates from $-\infty$ to ∞ .

If one considers the case of an infinite square well potential, one may see that $C\sin(n\pi x/L)$ wavelengths fit in. The entropy is:

$$S = \int_0^L dx \sum_{m=-s}^s \sin(n^*3/14x/L) \sin(n3.14x/L) \ln\{\sin(n^*3/14x/L) \sin(n3.14x/L)\} \quad ((3))$$

Now, one may change $dx \rightarrow n3.14dx/L$ ($L/n3.14$).

$$\text{This yields: } S = \ln(L/n3.14) + \ln(\text{entropy for a single cycle}) \quad ((4))$$

One sees $\ln(L/(n3.14))$ as similar to the extensive $\ln(L)$ from classical physics, but this time divided into the number of crests in the square well because these are resolution units. The second term in ((4)) is a kind of intrinsic entropy per crest.

The Case of an Eigenstate of SS , Sz

In (1), an equation is given for the entropy of a spin state measured along the z axis. It is assumed that this state contains various $m = -s$ to s projections.

$$S = - \sum_{m=-s}^s |a(s,m)|^2 \ln\{|a(s,m)|^2\} -$$

$$\int |b(\phi)|^2 \ln\{|b(\phi)|^2\} d\phi \quad ((5))$$

Here $b(\phi) = \sum_{m=-s}^s a(s,m) W(s,m)$ where $W(s,m) = \exp(i(s+m)\phi)$ for z in the northern part of a sphere and $\exp(i(-s+m)\phi)$ for z in the southern. $a(s,m)$ is defined using an eigenstate of SS and Sz , i.e.

$$|\text{state } s\rangle = \sum_{m=-s}^s a(s,m) |s,m\rangle \text{ where } |s,m\rangle \text{ is an eigenstate of } SS, \text{ and } Sz.$$

We noted in Part I that this equation seems to give 0 entropy for an eigenstate of SS and Sz as one knows this state fully. This is like the von Neumann entropy yielding 0 for a eigenstate of energy. We also note that in (1), $\exp(i(s+m)\phi)/\sqrt{2^*3.14}$, so m is not being used to define a intrinsic free range as in $\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest that if one has $|s, sz\rangle$ as an Sz , SS eigenstate, then one should have an intrinsic entropy linked to $\exp(im\phi)$. For the eigenstate measured along the z axis, one may use $\exp(im\phi)$ and, like with $\exp(ipx)$, define an intrinsic entropy as:

$$\text{Entropy of } |s, sz\rangle \text{ in terms of } \phi = \ln(2^*3.14 m) \quad ((6))$$

To obtain this result, one must assume a uniform distribution which follows from $\exp(-im\phi)$ $\exp(im\phi)$ as well as integrate over the appropriate $1/m$ range, not simply 0 to $2^*3.14$.

The question we then ask is what does one do if one considers $|s, sz\rangle$ from the point of view of the x -axis?

$|s=3/2, sz=3/2\rangle$ From the Point of View of the X-Axis

We consider $|s=3/2, sz=3/2\rangle$ as being linked with $\exp(i 3/2 \text{ phi})$ and as having an intrinsic entropy of:

$$S \text{ of } |s=3/2, sz=3/2\rangle \text{ from the point of view of the z-axis} = \ln(2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 3/2) \quad ((7))$$

To obtain this from $\exp(i 3/2 \text{ phi})$ one must take $\exp(i 3/2 \text{ phi}) \exp(-i 3/2 \text{ phi})$ and use the integration range linked to a period, i.e.

$$3/2 \text{ phi} = 2 \cdot 3.14 \text{ or } \text{phi} = 0 \text{ to } 2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot (2/3) \quad ((8))$$

If one considers measuring along the x-axis, then the spin matrix from (2) is:

$$\begin{matrix} .5 | & 0 & \text{sqrt}(3) & 0 & 0 | & ((9)) \\ | & \text{sqrt}(3) & 0 & 2 & 0 | \\ | & 0 & 2 & 0 & \text{sqrt}(3) | \\ | & 0 & 0 & \text{sqrt}(3) & 0 | \end{matrix}$$

We find the eigenstates to be:

$$S_x = 3/2 \quad 1/\text{sqrt}(8) \{ 1, -\text{sqrt}(3), \text{sqrt}(3), -1 \} \quad ((10))$$

$$s_x = 1/2 \quad \text{sqrt}(3)/\text{sqrt}(8) \{ 1, -1/\text{sqrt}(3), -1/\text{sqrt}(3), 1 \}$$

$$s_x = -1/2 \quad \text{sqrt}(3/8) \{ 1, 1/\text{sqrt}(3), -1/\text{sqrt}(3), -1 \}$$

$$s_x = -3/2 \quad \text{sqrt}(1/8) \{ 1, \text{sqrt}(3), \text{sqrt}(3), 1 \}$$

We next try to write $(1,0,0,0)$ i.e. $sz=3/2$ in terms of the s_x basis:

$$(1,0,0,0) = 1/\text{sqrt}(8) |s_x=3/2\rangle + \text{sqrt}(3/8) |s_x=1/2\rangle + \text{sqrt}(3/8) |s_x=-1/2\rangle + \text{sqrt}(1/8) |s_x=-3/2\rangle \quad ((11))$$

Then we write two terms for entropy, just as in (1), namely an entropy for having an s_x eigenstate as well as a term linked to the phi entropy. The first term is:

$$- \left(\frac{1}{8} \ln(\frac{1}{8}) \cdot 2 + 3 \cdot \frac{3}{8} \ln(\frac{3}{8}) \right) \quad ((12)) \quad (\text{For } s_z \text{ measurements, this entropy is 0.})$$

To calculate the phi entropy, we suggest writing ((11)) in terms of $\exp(im \text{ phi})$, where phi is linked to the x axis, i.e.

$$W(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}} \exp(i \frac{3}{2} \phi) + \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} \exp(-i \frac{1}{2} \phi) + \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} \exp(i \frac{1}{2} \phi) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{8}} \exp(-i \frac{3}{2} \phi) \quad ((13))$$

We suggest creating a classical type probability, $W^*(\phi)W(\phi)$, but note suggest $W(\phi)$ is a periodic function and that one must choose a periodic ϕ range.

To find the periodicity of $W(\phi)$ we use:

$$\frac{3}{2} \phi = n_1 2\pi \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{2} \phi = n_2 2\pi \quad \text{so that} \quad 4\pi \quad \text{yields periodicity for both } \frac{1}{2} \text{ and } \frac{3}{2} \quad ((14))$$

Thus, the entropy as seen from the z axis is very different from that as seen from the x -axis. We suggest that entropy is linked to the measurement made and not an absolute.

We suggest that using the above ideas, one may obtain an entropy for $|s=3/2, s_z=3/2\rangle$ as seen from the x -axis.

One may repeat the calculation for $|s=3/2, s_z=1/2\rangle$. In this case, $1/\sqrt{8}$ applies to $s_x=1/2$ and $s_x=-1/2$, but with different signs and $\sqrt{3/8}$ applies to $s_x=3/2$ and $s_x=-3/2$. One sees in this case, how negative weights can appear in $W(\phi)$ in quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue $\exp(ipx)$ should have an intrinsic entropy linked to the wavelength length and that one may ignore the infinite length of space as the particle is not bound. We suggest a uniform distribution and an entropy of $\ln(p/hbar)$. We suggest that for a pure spin projection along z , i.e. eigenstate of S_S and S_z , one should also have an intrinsic entropy given by: $\ln(2\pi \cdot m)$. This means taking $\exp(im\phi) \cdot \exp(-im\phi)$, but also integrating over a period of this function and not over 2π . In other words, $\exp(im\phi)$ contains its own special ϕ range for periodicity as does $\exp(ipx)$.

We suggest that the formula in (1) seems to deal with a mixed state entropy, i.e. uses a $|s, s_z=m_1\rangle + b |s, s_z=m_2\rangle$ etc to calculate an entropy linked to both the weights a, b and ϕ values associated with $\exp(im\phi)$.

We suggest here using the formula of (1) for an S_z eigenstate, seen by a person on the x axis, but restricting the ϕ range to the periodic value of:

$$|s, s_z\rangle = a_1 |s, s_x=-m\rangle + a_2 |s, s_x=-m+1\rangle + \dots \quad \text{and} \quad |s, s_x=m\rangle. \quad ((B))$$

One piece of the entropy is given by $-\sum_i a_i \ln(a_i)$. This is 0 as seen along the z -axis.

The other piece is given by writing (B) with $|s, s_x = m\rangle = \exp(im\phi)$, but finding a periodic ϕ range (ϕ linked to x) when integrating using $P(\phi) = W^*(\phi)W(\phi)$ and using Shannon's entropy.

We give an example using $s=3/2$ and $s_z=3/2$.

References

1. Geger, D. and Kedem, Z. Spin Entropy (2022) Entropy 2022, 24(9), 1292;
<https://doi.org/10.3390/e24091292> <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/24/9/1292>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/3D_rotation_group#A_note_on_Lie_algebra